

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS AND AI IN LANGUAGE LEARNING AND COMMUNICATION

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Annotation: Advancements in modern technology, especially Artificial intelligence, have transformed how people acquire languages and communicate. AI-driven platforms, tools and social websites all offer enough resources to learn languages and speak in them at the same time. They provide personalized, interactive learning paths, assistance in all aspects of any language; listening, reading, writing, speaking, grammar, pronunciation, and others. AI tutors, virtual reality, 3d grammar lessons, and AI chatbots can make the process easier and quicker than expected. However, its use in education can also be hazardous if it is used as a form of cheating or getting personal information. This study examines the value of AI in language acquisition and communication, as well as its advantages, disadvantages, realistic solutions and prospects. Even if it is considered to be effective, social interaction is still important, and a well-thought-out strategy can ensure the balance in terms of its usage.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, AI-driven platforms, Virtual reality, AI tutor, AI chatbots, personalized learning paths.

Introduction

In today's world, there have been significant developments in the field of technology. One of them is artificial intelligence (AI). The release of AI to the

world made the workload of many spheres smoother and faster. As a part of this, education is also taking advantage of it, and we can see people who are learning foreign languages, occupations, for example. Particularly, more and more people are acquiring languages and having communication with the help of a wide range of AI-based resources, making learning go without extra difficulties. Nevertheless, it may create some problems with students, such as overreliance on it and lack of human interaction. In these cases, we should try to alleviate them because these problems can give rise to other ones. Since people make use of it to improve their language and communication skills, there is an ongoing debate about whether it is a good development or not. That's why this thesis aims to explore both the benefits and drawbacks of using AI and questions how we can find better solutions to reduce the downsides and use it only for our self-improvement.

Main information

The rise of AI in education has paved the way for shaping education at many points. It is rich in resources, and with its help, learning any language has become quite straightforward. Here are some benefits coming from using AI in the language learning process.

1. Enhanced personalized education.

If you want to learn a language and ask to provide some sources to use from it, it first asks about your learning details: your interests, style, and pace. After getting to know you deeply, it analyzes your responses, then suggests the most favourable ones. This way with AI can be applied to teaching in a classroom setting where teachers give information about their students' preferences and conduct the lessons by considering everything. Here, they try to organize classes generally in a way that can satisfy everyone's needs so that no one needs to pay attention to other things. While decisions in general classroom environments are mostly shaped by the general situation of the class, it can be thought that a learning environment that can meet students' needs can be created in classes where AI technologies are integrated. It is very important to capture a parallelism between

individual students' needs and the learning goal (Yigit, 2024). To reveal students' interests and abilities, Big Data analysis that can identify their needs as well as abilities can be performed.

2. Blended learning.

As a part of face-to-face classes, online classes can be established among students who have health problems and are not physically there. For instance, the platform "Zoom" incorporates AI to enhance the meeting experience. It enables everyone to participate in the lessons without truancy. Especially, it is applicable to teach languages to disabled students who cannot go and attend real school lessons.

3. Intriguing learning process.

There are a vast number of apps that were launched to teach languages by entertaining the learners, such as Duolingo, Memrise, LingQ, and FluentU. They were designed in a way that it feels like you are playing a game, not learning a language. However, in a similar vein, you are learning new grammar structures, words, and idioms, but not consciously. They make you repeat the words over and over again, listen to the audios, read the texts, speak in different contexts, and do the provided activities. Doing so daily, you can get accustomed to learning something in the target language.

Besides, there are certain platforms specialised in testing the covered topics like Kahoot, Quizziz, Quizlet, and so on. They create a competent learning atmosphere where participants move towards winning. Learning exists here also, since students can have an opportunity to learn from their mistakes, one of the most effective learning methods.

Using virtual reality (VR) when explaining the theme is another fruitful method to make learning interesting. Here, teachers allow their students to interact with real-world scenarios, enhancing engagement, comprehension, and retention. Since students learn new information through different senses (sight, hearing, smell, taste, and touch), the rate of learning materials increases when they see the objects and creatures, touch them, and hear their sounds. Examining the affective

benefits of AI-assisted language learning, Renders and Vattana (2014) revealed a significant improvement in students' confidence, perceived competence, and WTC, and lowered anxiety in the game-play environment after six sessions (C. Zhang, 2024). So, from these points, we can deduce that AI-based games, lessons not only cultivate a fascinating vibe, but also eliminate the psychological problems.

5. Increased speaking skills.

AI-driven websites and apps like ChatGPT, Deepseek, Yandex, Gemini and others can have conversations with people in any language they use to talk to them. That is why they sound like a native speaker, and it is also a chance to interact with them and improve our pronunciation step by step. Plus, they provide brief and instant feedback to focus on the weakest sides. Speaking in that way has a huge influence on the fluency of that language, and being disciplined helps to accelerate the process by getting noticeable changes. This, in turn, boosts their confidence and speaking skills, leading to active participation in classroom discussions, contributing to higher levels of WTC and FLE, and lower levels of FLA (C. Zhang, 2024).

However, it does not mean that using AI for language acquisition and communication has only advantages; it also has some disadvantages, which are taking their toll on the education system in Uzbekistan, as well. Here, we list primary problems occurring right now:

1. Lack of human interaction.

Despite the advantages of AI apps for language learning and assessment, it is crucial to recognize that they may reduce face-to-face contact in EFL classrooms. For students to participate in genuine and meaningful dialogues, direct connection with instructors and peers is essential (L. Elliott, 2023). AI chatbots can replicate discussions but cannot fully capture the subtleties and dynamics of interpersonal dialogue (J. Jeon, 2021).

2. Pleasure and entertainment.

Students sometimes should be deprived of having only frequent games, so

that they are not problematic to control and teach. Moreover, it is good for their attention span, as the ones who are addicted to playing games are not prone to read long texts, doing activities, and listening to lesson audios.

3. Ethical concerns.

AI in the EFL classroom raises significant ethical questions about data security and privacy. AI systems gather and examine learner data, including performance and personal data (L. Elliott, 2023). To solve this issue, we have to check first whether the app or website we are using is reliable, fair and inclusive, so that we will not end up having these dilemmas.

Another suggestion is not exposing ourselves to the media openly. AI has reached the level where it is possible to get personal information by hacking. So, if we want security, we must not post anything about ourselves or show ourselves.

Conclusion

All in all, AI is inevitable; it is our today and future. In the era where most industries are connected to it, we also have to initiate its use in education due to the benefits above. There will be significant advancements in education if we learn how to use it for which purposes. The problems can be easily resolved by balance and discipline. We have to use our chances and make the most of them as much as possible.

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